

Join the European Policymaker and Advisory Networks for Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs)

Now is your chance to join the first-ever European networks focused on Short Food Supply Chains (SFSCs).

These networks are part of the Horizon Europe projects EU4Advice and COREnet.

Our aim: to enhance the sustainability, competitiveness, and visibility of SFSCs across Europe.

Are you an advisor supporting SFSC farmers and producers?

This is a voluntary, flexible opportunity to grow your impact, build valuable connections, and contribute to shaping the future of food systems in Europe!

Why join?

- ✓ Connect with a wide community of SFSC experts and advisors
- ✓ Access training materials, workshops, and knowledge-sharing sessions
- ✓ Participate in networking and policy-shaping activities
- ✓ Access best practices, training materials & legal resources
- ✓ Be listed in a public database as a trusted SFSC advisor

Register now!

Are you a policymaker passionate about sustainable food systems?

Become part of a network of trusted policymakers and help shape future recommendations for resilient, local food systems across the EU!

Why join?

- ✓ Stay ahead of EU policy developments
- ✓ Collaborate with peers across Europe
- ✓ Share challenges and solutions from your region
- ✓ Access best practices, training materials & legal resources
- ✓ Connect with SFSC producers, advisors, and EU projects

Register now!

